

Local Government in Italy

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Italy: An Introduction

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According to the legal framework resulting from the 2001 constitutional reform - and progressively entering into force - local authorities, i.e., municipalities, provinces and metropolitan cities - shall be financed by means of own tax sources, shared taxes, non-earmarked equalization transfers, plus additional transfers provided for exceptional cases (Article 119 Constitution). However, over the last decade (2010-2020) local finance has witnessed a structural metamorphosis marked by an overall increase of local taxes and a correspondent decrease (-32 per cent) of state transfers altogether considered.⁷³ At present, local financing is mostly based on taxes, which are created and regulated in their foundations by the central level of government (so-called devolved taxes).

Having specific regard to municipalities, they are vested with a tax varying power and/or are entitled to the revenue generated within their territory. In 2018, the share of local taxes compared to overall local revenues was 46 per cent and this figure has been increasing. This is the result of frequent revisions adopted by national legislation from 2012 onwards. Since 2014 one of the major municipal tax sources is the *Imposta Unica Comunale* (literally, Single Municipal Tax), composed of a local tax on property of housing (IMU), a local tax on waste (TARI) and a local tax for general public services provided by the municipalities (TASI). Local taxes also include a surtax on individual income (IRPEF), consisting of a fixed tax rate defined by national law, which resembles a shared tax, and an optional tax rate which can be determined by each municipality within an upper limit of 0,8 per cent. Tax benefits can be set within the limits provided by the national legislation. Autonomous own tax sources represent an exception to this scheme. The tourist tax is one example: a national law entitles municipalities to impose a tourist tax to be applied within the upper limit set by the state (Legislative Decree no 23/2011).

In order to remedy inter-municipal imbalances, the state has set up an equalization fund providing for non-earmarked transfers. Since the constitutional reform of 2001, the overall system of equalization is undergoing a comprehensive reform. According to Article 119(4) of the Constitution, a state law shall establish a non-earmarked equalization fund, to be assigned to entities with lower fiscal capacity per-capita. At the same time, the state holds the exclusive legislative power over the equalization system and over the determination of the fundamental functions of local entities to be ensured in a uniform manner across the country (Article 117(2) Constitution).

⁷³ All data in the text are taken from: IFEL Dipartimento Finanza Locale, 'La finanza comunale in sintesi. Rapporto 2019' (IFEL 2019) <https://www.fondazioneifel.it/documenti-e-pubblicazioni/item/download/3410_1784abea3a086d86f6363eaf17c6d78f>.

This framework was implemented partly by Law no 42/2009, partly by a number of governmental decrees. In particular, Law no 42/2009 requires the gradual overcoming of the funding system, which links the transfers to the resources spent in the previous financial years (so-called historic spending). The new calculation of the funding shall be based on objective and pre-defined parameters to be applied uniformly to all entities (so-called standard costs and needs). Pursuant to Article 11, two equalization mechanisms shall be established on the basis of a twofold classification of the decentralized functions. A first scheme has to ensure the funding of fundamental functions (around 80 per cent of local spending), while a second one is envisaged for the other residual (non-fundamental) functions (20 per cent of local spending). The impact of equalization differs between the two groups: a full financing is foreseen for fundamental functions, while only a partial equalization is prescribed for all others. A second differentiation consists in the financing parameter: equalization transfers are calculated applying the standard costs and needs criteria to the first group only, while for non-fundamental functions equalization is related to the per-capita fiscal capacity.

The regulation of these equalization mechanisms (methodology and definition of parameters) has been left to governmental decrees (e.g., Law Decree no 216/2010 as later modified and integrated), while a public-private company (SOSE) is in charge of calculating the standard costs and needs. These have to be calculated for each fundamental function taking into consideration the peculiarities of the single function and each category of entity (e.g. the size of municipalities).

Within this complex legal framework, the Stability Law 2013 (Law no 228/2012) has finally set up the Fund of Municipal Solidarity, as later modified by the Stability Law 2014 (Law no 147/2013, paragraph 729). However, the transition towards the new system started only in 2015. The Fund is financed through a share of the revenue generated from the local tax on properties - IMU (accounting for 38.23 per cent in 2015 and for 24.43 per cent in 2016) and only a selection of local tax revenues is taken as benchmark, in order to determine who is entitled to benefit from it. In 2016, the resources of the equalization fund that were distributed on the basis of the new standardized parameters amounted to only 30 per cent, while the rest was allocated taking into account historic spending (the old parameter). The share is progressively increasing, and the new system should enter fully into force in 2021.

Starting from 2015, spending autonomy of local entities has expanded significantly. The Internal Stability Pact has been abandoned and a new system based on the principle of balanced budget is in place.⁷⁴ The impact of the principle of 'balanced budget' for local authorities has been specified by Article 9 of Law no 243/2012, as later modified by Law no 164/2016. It prescribes the achievement (paragraph 1) of a non-negative value - on accrual basis - in the balance between final revenues and final expenditures. The new legal framework imposes limits to deficits and to the possibility to incur debts and, at the same time, it sets strict limitations to overspending. Deviations from the equilibrium could occur after agreement

⁷⁴ In this respect, see also report section 3.2. on Investment Spending of Local Entities.

reached at the regional level or at the national level, among all territorial entities and/or with the State. These allow for compensatory measures, potentially releasing space to single entities for investment spending. It is not by chance, then, that in the last few years the use of other sources of funding, such as the use of public-private partnerships (project finance, leasing) or EU resources, has increased.

All in all, municipalities do not receive other transfers, with minor exceptions. One example consists in the measures in favor of tiny municipalities with less than 5,000 inhabitants. In 2017 the Fund for Structural, Economic and Social Development has been set up and it is distributed on the basis of parameters that serve to safeguard of the environment and the cultural heritage, as well as the economic, social and infrastructural development of small municipalities. In addition, to cope with the challenge of increasingly depopulated small municipalities forms of reduced taxation have been introduced, for foreigners that move their residence in small municipalities of the south.

Also the financing of provinces and metropolitan cities, the system is based on the same type of sources, i.e., devolved and shared taxes, plus transfers from the experimental fund for financial consolidation of provinces. However, the legal framework is even more complex and uncertain. As to the provinces, this is the result of the austerity measures that have progressively reduced the transfers, on the one hand, and of the undergoing process of territorial reorganization regarding in particular the (reduction of) functions allocated to the provincial level. As to metropolitan cities, the situation is even more uncertain: they have been finally established by Law no 56/2014, but their system of financing remains undefined. The result is that the provincial scheme with reduced resources still applies to them entailing problems of underfunded mandates.⁷⁵

Notwithstanding the discrepancies among the single local entities in terms of population size and density, territorial and socio-economic characteristics, all local entities of a certain type are vested with the same competences and the same system of financing applies. However, the system described above applies to local entities within ordinary regions. For special regions, the rules are different. First, the general financial rules do not directly apply to them, but they have been asked to reform their systems according to the same basic principles. The specific regulations have to be agreed between each special region and the state in bilateral negotiations. In sum, special regions enjoy a higher degree of financial autonomy, but they differ one from the other to a great extent. Second, some special regions are in charge of local finance, whereas in others this remains a state competence. But it is the responsibility of all regions (special and ordinary) to ensure the respect of the balanced budget principle taking into account all territorial entities within the regional territory of reference.

⁷⁵ Commissione Parlamentare per l'Attuazione del Federalismo Fiscale, 'Resoconto Stenografico' (Audizione 99, 23 February 2017) 5
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